

zllac&ll aeawmfpOf ||igonf pty&mZlw yvifu&&ef yg&rBq, fy¹ w&m;wll
ajrmufm;pñ jznfusi qntfy;vsuf av;toacEsh urñwpoef, MumumvywvW
usi fvtc&vlyD pav;toacñ urñwpoef, Mumumv ywvW pty&mZlwyvifu
&&ef welfmqilybaom Obaqifawmull jzwl vsclbn/ rsulfawmftplwll
vnfaumif? Eshom;ulvnfaumif xkwl vsclbn/ ZmvDrifom;Esh orðawmf
uPñZefullvnfaumif? r' ð' Oubbaom Zedullvnfaumif tvsclyk&vlltm;
ulefyklytcl flluef vsclbn/ pyvifonf b&m; \ rm&li g;yg;ull wppr-ufy, &S f
atmifri&myvifvnt jzpay\? blef, Muuba&r*fv&llum vepñjri rwaom
yvivnt;jzpay\ / pty&mZlw yviü xll ðepOlyif b&m;jzpef Bupñawmikv
vllm;orull jynpñkuefyD prausZt Burm;aom yvifawmñS igonfxao;}} [k
BupñlyDvif ul# toef, ru rsm;vñbaom t& [w&llv pwkvpñef ormywvll
Oipm;vsuf xllty&mZlwyvifawmñxurñyif clep&ullum olvifol xll ðeawmñav
onf

jrwpñb&m;onf uqefvjynhaumf 1-&uñel waelywvWul# toef
rurm;pñbaom t& [w&llv pwkvpñef ormywvll Oipm;vsuf Oñkvtçrfom
(t& [w&llvçrfom)ull çpm;awmñli xll uqefvjynhaumf 1-&uf nOD, ði y#pñoryj' f
w&m;awmull tOZñypö m ocñ&m tOZñ [ðom talumifalumi h ylnmbocñ&
tylnmbocñ& tmaelñbocñ& [ðom ocñ&omñst wñzi h ob&mO# 'lu² jzppOull
tEkmr tm;jzifvnfaumif? tOZñ, awD taoO O&m*ed&ma"m ocñ&ed&ma"m-
t& [wñ*zi h tOZñw&m; tuçfr&ñçyjiçfalumi h ocñ&omñst wñçyfi Muonf/poñzi h
ob&m O#f lu² çypOwñf, [ðom y#ñvmr tm;jzi h Eshom; qifçifawmñavonf²

xll y#pñoryj' w&m;ull tEkmñ#vlltm;jzi h tzezeboñoyqifçifawmñbaom
tcg jrwpñb&m; \ a½OPawmñu tOZñtp&ñom talumifw&m;alumi h ocñ& tp&ñom
tustw&m;wll r&yfrem;jzplyñ;rlwñf, [ðom ob&mO#f lu² jzppOf tEkmñ oabmEsh
tOZñtp&ñom talumifw&m;wll çyjiçfalumi h ocñ& tp&ñom tustw&m;wll
çyñi ðfrlwnf, [ðom ob&mO#f lu² çypOly#vll teubabmwll wñi wñi
xiviçobmojzi h jrwpñb&m; \ Eshom; [', Owñay:ü Eñpouf
Orñajrmuçifyvllw&m; Obaqimionh r [mbud maomreó o [*IP? ÓPorj kwf
tocñ&du aZmtpOwll wocñ&ocñ&fjzpiñ aeavonf³

tllçultwçfol axmywñzppap quñzppap avmifí xññomtcg xll tllçulwll
jynñi yllñomaxmywqbnf tjyibll xçulfmulef oubll jrwpñb&m; \
Esh tñfñ w&m;oabmwñznlyDvif Orñwçfürqñ tjyibll vçulfmonñyrm
xlynmÓPñ&ñobñ;ñom yvllulltalumi jykñ , 'g [aO ygvllbOEñ "rñ-tp&ñom
ol*gxmulust; ði ðawmñavonf⁴

¹ 'geyg&rD olv yg&rD aeufyg&rD ynmyg&rD O&d yg&rD cEñyg&rD opinyg&rD t''d meyg&rD arwinyg&rD
Oayumygy&rD
² tax&x&A [lkw rmwllumusrf? 146-147/
³ r [mAR Oi P ' R 355-356/
⁴ r [mAR Oi P ' R 356-357/
⁵ r [mAR Oi P ' R 357/

pwkwəwā[oħ&muāomtçg jrwpñb&monf r[maAm''yifStæmuf
ajrmuāxmiħ t&yf ewfA[mwl zeqiftyaom &wemC&a½tçfū xuD, f
zħacpħawmñlum]tbd'rñy#u} w&m;awmñrwlūoħoyqijci fawmñravonf¹

&wemC&a½tçfū xuD, zħacpħawmñlum w&m;awmñul oħoyqijcifi
a0æ, sowðgtaygiful Mun&qijci fawmñraom u&wñlūāomol ewvl jA[m
owðgwñbnf obvulvññi orm''pəvlul wñlunī atmi fymñvðfi ynmjziħ
Oyó emtm;xkwusi buli r* zħveāħefwnf [ħom t&d mbħbħ&muñlūāumif ob?
orm''ā ynmwnf [ħom y#ywf vrfp0vrf;allumif,ul aumi fñojri fawmñbojziħ
a&S0pñ obvul jyq&m Oēnty#u ubiqijci fawmñraonf/ xħemuf orm''ul
jyq&m okvief y#uul oħoyqijci fawmñravonf/ xħemuf ynmñlyq&m tbd'rñ
y#uul oħoyqijci fawmñravonf²

tbd'rñy#u w&m;awmñsm;ul oħoyqijci fawmñraomtçg "rə*Plust?
Obifust? "mwluxmurt? yf*vyūwulust? uxñOwħ urf? , rñlūurtwlū
oħoyqijci fawmñraomtçlū oAñkwā½OPi awmñ us, Defñyð w&m;ent;u
uðf;ojziħ a&mi fcnħawmñajcmufy; ruējrl; ao;yj clepqijci fawmñzpnñħ teEē,
orEj|me fust;buðul oħoyqijci fawmñraomtçg oAñkwā½OPāwmñ uējrl;av
onf³

teEē, orEj|me fust;buðwñf tvēbōħarE;ñeueħom w&m; tcsulwlū
oħoyqijci fawmñraomtçg jrwpñb&mon\oEħeū tvēf Eñpouf Orfajrmujci f
yñvñw&m;jzpyñ;vmavonf⁴

yñvñw&m; jzpyñ;aomañumiħ aofawmñunñvi fawonf/ aofawmñ Munñvijci f
añumiħ ta&awmñ Munñvi fawonf/ ta&awmñunñvijci fañumiħ a&mi fcnħawmñwl onf
xūay:uējrl;ñuī teEēñlūOVmwñ f a&mi fcnñuejrl;avonf⁵

y|me f;w&m;awmñul oħoyqijci fawmñraonñħ xħelū jrwpñb&mon\ ul fawmñs
xūay:uējrl;ñuāom a&mi fcnħawmñraonñ , aelwl ħatmi fyi teEēñlūOVm
avmu''mwñwlūOwñZ½yf tququftæ t xm;jziħoñ;vsuf &ñuueñ⁶

y|me f;w&m;awmñonñ aumi fui fubñ enfaygif teEēñjynpñ? ajrBuðxk
ymñyēus, mñ? ork &ma&xlyrm eueñvñ/ xħbyjzpnñ vñf; oAñkw
ā½OPāwmñubñ Buðrm;vsi jreñvāomañumiħ clep&ujzi fyi oħoyf qijci fci fupō
ñyðqħavonf/ xħwl w&m;&wemul qijci fawmñraonñ ĩclep&uywñvl aēawmñ&m
t&yonñ]]&wemC&apwñ [ĩ rñwñ fawonf

(5) tZyg v owñ[

¹ r [mAR Oi P ' R 364/
² r [mAR Oi P ' R 364/
³ r [mAR Oi P ' R 364-365/
⁴ r [mAR Oi P ' R 365/
⁵ r [mAR Oi P ' R 365/
⁶ r [mAR Oi P ' R 370-371/

xhæmuf jrwpðb&m;onf r[maAm''yiN teðüif av;owän [(28-&u) wluð
 ulefvæpNyðæmuf ylröwän [oð&muðæomtçg r[maAm''yif rst a&ßt&yüwn&ðom
 tZygvannimiyi&i;foð uð&muðæwmrlyðvüf clep&uf ywfvðw&m;uðqijcifum
 zvormywuðipm;í tZygv annimiyi&i;fü öwif,öæxðæwmrion/ xhænmiyif
 &yðoð qðváusim; om;rsn; vma&muðæxð rrsn;amUmih tZygvannimiyif [lí wðáv
 onf¹

xltçg trðtrnftm;jzih rxi&ð;aom w[lef [lef;merjcið oabm&ðom
 ylpð;wpa, muðonf jrwpðb&m;xlbð cðfuylyðvüf jrwpðb&m;ES h EpvDrta;rmuf
 zG þum;uðajymUm;Nyðæmuf oiðvsmuf yw&mt&yü &ylyðvü b&m;&S fuð

]]avmuü tb, rðæom w&m;jzih jAm [Pac: ojrwpipþjzpf
 eðlygoent? ojrwpjzpatmif jykvvæom w&m;rsn;um; tb, f w&m;
 rsn;jzplygoent}} [lar;awmrionf²

raumitruð tyjylyðjzpjcið? rmerhruipijcið? ze&nlywþeðrl uitpijcið?
 övjziðwESvluð apmiðæf;çslylyðjzpjcið? t& [w&lvf (ölr [kv) eðæföð&muðlyð
 jzpjcið? r*lvnf [æom jrwaomtusi luð tlyðwð lusi bonyðjzpjcið w&m;wES jynþm
 ouð jAm [Pac: onf [k a [mawmrion/ xhæmuf jrwpðb&m;onf rm&ewf
 orðoðæ, muþjzpaom wPð? t&wð &m*wð vma&muð jzm;a, mifonluð
 jrwpðb&m;&S fu &m* w&m;wly, Nyðæmuf a [mawmrion/ o [rüvjA [muðonf
 jrwpðb&m;xuð öv*P! orm''ðP! ynm*P! ÖðkwðPwð omvæbor&ðUmif
 öð*gxmjziðvðuðxm;onf jrwpðb&m;onf o [rüvjA [mawmi;yeçsuf ES luð kvð f
 ölyðæom w&m;wluð t½ttao tav; tjrwjyki æonf/pü xð [k lylyPð;tm;
 jrwpðb&m;onf w&m;emçjyki w&m;a [map&mrl opðav;yg;w&m;uð xðxçfí
 öðnr [kvðrðN - "rðmUm w&m;uðra [mrd jrwpðb&m; ½ðvqð [mlUm;tyðæom
 w&m;*gxmuð Num;em &aomöwltm; wyb? bvðu uleðonfðæmiwltm;
 öP*ly;jcið rstublyif Ögoembm*d rðm tust&eðlon? opðav;yg; w&m;uð
 xðxçf;ojri lum r*lvayguðfra&muðeðacs, if,öjzpjciðrðn "rðvmyifjzponf³

xlbð xð [k lylyPð;rðn w&m;a' oem\ wn&mr [kvf (opðav;yg;w&m;
 ojririðnr [kv)öjzih jrwpðb&m;onf [k lylyPð;uð w&m;emçt &mxm; awmrlyl
 xlyPð;ar;avðuðonh teuft''yðj, luð öð&awmrion-a, m jAm [Pm Am [wvygy''arð-
 tþ&ðom O'gef*gxmuð uð;&ih awmravon/ xluð jrwpðb&m;onf
 qðváusim;anmiyü (7)&uf ywfvð ply, æwmr&m t&yðonf]]tZygvowän [}}
 rnN/⁴

(6) rðwæ'owän [

¹ r [mAK'Oi? 'R 372/

² r [mAK'Oi? 'R 373/

³ r [mAK'Oi? 'R 375/

⁴ r [mAK'Oi? 'R 391/

- ri[*P! Al*, majrjwr [m/ (2011)/ *Graphic Design Kyaw Minn Maung/ aZ, smajrpmay? &efule/*
 Anm; v? trwbu/ (1967)/ *&mZm''&mZfta&awmy/Lsr/ elbmyElywLul &efule/*
- Alu? r&v/ (1984)/ *jA [p&dl ofiz# \ xijcm;aomtaetxm;/ ÓPvi# "rþmya' om 10tlyajrmul*
txtxw? ynmAmeyElywLul &efule/
- Opwvóm&mbOb? (00)/ (2002)/ *wy#u''&q&mawm? E#i#hwMAl omoe r [mAl Oil 'kwj w#*
omoema&Obp)XmeyElywLul
- ouwi? (00)/ (1974)/ *apw#ygi# 58qbr#ftuOfcsyl oZiyElywLul &efule/*
- [wpef (00)/ (1951)/ *y' w#Íkom [hom ygvj#refmtbd'mel crf,om a&mi pllyElywLul &efule/*